

Protecting the interests of Owners of Digital Contents in Open Access Movement

Dr. Swapan Khan

Librarian, Narasinha Dutt College, 129, Belilious Road, Howrah

E-mail: khanswapan@gmail.com

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Abstract: *The offline business model for promoting digital goods has been replaced by an online model due to the rapid advancement of information technology, strong user demand, and growing reliance on the internet facilities. In addition, digital content needs to be made available online by removing any restrictions on access in order to maximize accessibility. The Open Access Movement is growing and advocates for information without barriers. The primary goal of the Open Access movement is to improve the system of scientific communication so that optimal access of information is confirmed. This concept sometimes works against protecting the interests of content creators or content owners. The present study focuses on the areas for preserving the interest of the owners of digital contents by analysing various technologies, laws and regulation.*

Keywords: Open Access Movement, Digital Rights Management, Copyright, Digital Resource, Free Resources, Digital Content

1. Introduction

Open access resources are accessible to all the users without any barrier such as free of cost etc. These resources are available in public domain such as internet. In simple words "Open access literature is digital, online, free of charge, and free of most copyright and licensing restrictions" (Open Access, n.d.). The main goals of open access are to address three significant issues: equity, affordability, and accessibility. But more than two decades after its inception, the Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI) has manifestly failed to address the latter two issues (Anderson, 2023).

To protect the interest of owners of the scholarly publications and other stakeholders is another very important issue in OA movement. The owner of a copyright is granted the sole authority to duplicate, distribute, create derivative works, and present a work in public. The copyright holder needs sales in order to benefit financially from the work. However, copyright limits the public's access to knowledge due to its financial interests (Karthiayani A. 2020). OA movement grants the open access licenses which concept supports the copyleft. Copyleft is a legal strategy that permits certain liberties over copies of works protected by copyright, provided that derivative works maintain the same rights. By using the copyleft policies open access movements can be geared up but it should be kept in mind that both the owners of the contents and the users must accept the terms and conditions. The present paper

focuses the use of copyrighted scholarly publishing in open access movement and preserves the moral rights of the content owners.

2 Objectives

The threat of the fair use domain contracting is brought about by the production and publication of copyrighted digital content over time. Encouraging legitimate and equitable uses of digital copyrighted works is crucial for users in OA movement. In this setting the main objectives of this study are as follows:

- to outline open access initiatives around the world;
- to state various Digital Rights Management (DRM) technologies;
- to know the areas of activities those violate the owners' interest;
- to find out the possibilities of libraries for supporting OA movements.

3 Review of Literature

Giving intellectual property rights to standards, according to many end consumers of copyrighted products, leads to monopoly issues and increases the danger of societal benefit and utility being diminished (Patterson, 2000). To the detriment of all humanity, any obstacle placed in this way could hinder or delay progress (Nayak & Khanna, 2020). But it is true that scientific repeatability and integrity depend on open and accessible data, so that scientific knowledge must be available to the general public as soon as possible after publication (Parikh, Malcom & Moran, 2022). Information access is important for reasons of societal development as a whole. Moreover, access to information is the rights to culture and education. But it is true that "recognizing moral rights on the economic interests of the copyright owner" (Karthiayani, 2020) is very crucial. Scheufen (2015) suggests hybrid OA models to partially fulfill the principles of OA publishing. In academic publications, it should be shift from the close access to open access model in future (Scheufen, 2015). Though eliminating copyright and implementing open access everywhere might effectively mean the demise of hundreds of nonprofit scientific journals (Halsted, 2003). Therefore, to maintain a balance between the interests of two parties open access publishers need to know the basics of copyright and licensing system, technologies, policies etc. as a whole in publishing setting (Morrison & Desautels, 2016). The present study explores such areas for both of the parties.

4 Open Access Initiatives

The commercialization of higher education in the US, UK, Europe, and other parts of the world is a part of the history of the open access movement, as is the tale of committed individuals who defended their academic communities and resisted the attempts of multinational corporate publishing groupings to undermine scholarly research (Open Access, n.d.). The idea was started by sharing online access of journal articles. Since the 1970s, computer scientists have been self-archiving in anonymous file transfer protocols (History of open access, August 16, 2024).

1999 - 2000

The electronic preprints repository known as e-prints is founded by American physicist Paul Ginsparg in 1991 (it was renamed to ArXiv.org in 1999). It is the first website to instantly make scientific preprints available to the entire world (Open Access, n.d.). The 1990s serials issue was sparked by the escalating expenses associated with obtaining academic books. A large number of academic

institutions and research centers have contracted with private publishers to publish their works. In 1993, Open Society Foundation was created and in 1997 SciELO network was formed in Brazil. Public Knowledge Project (PKP) is founded by John Willinsky in the Faculty of Education at UBC in 1998. PKP has created the Open Conference Systems (2000), Open Journal Systems (2001), Open Harvester Systems (2002) and the Open Monograph Press (2013) (2013) (Oberländer, March 6, 2024). BioMed Central and the Public Library of Science (PLOS) were formed in 2000.

2001 - 2010

The Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI) was framed in December 2001. The Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) launches on May 12, 2003, with 300 titles (Koçak & Kiran, 2024). Research Councils UK (RCUK) release their “Position Statement on Open Access to Research Outputs,” in 2005 and in the same year the Wellcome Trust launches its Open Access Policy (wellcome.org). Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) is launched in 2009 (OpenAIRE history, n.d.).

2011 – 2020

In 2012, The Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB), a peer-reviewed open access book directory, is launched by the OAPEN Foundation (About DOAB, n.d.). President Obama signs the Digital Accountability and Transparency Act (DATA Act) on May 9, 2014 (Bricceno, June 9, 2014). Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) declared plans to require open access to research submitted to the next Research Excellence Framework in 2014 (Suber, August 8, 2012). The Open Library of Humanities (OLH) was formed in 2015. Covid-19 in 2020 speeds up the use of open-access preprint servers worldwide.

2020 – till now

An Action Plan for Diamond Open Access is released by Science Europe, COALition S, OPERAS, and the French National Research Agency (ANR) (EUA signs Action Plan for Diamond Open Access, March 9, 2022). The world’s first ever diamond open access global summit is held at Toluca, Mexico on October 23-27, 2023. It was co-organised by Science Europe and partners, including Redalyc, UAEMéx, AmeliCA, UNESCO, CLACSO, and others (Open Access, n.d.).

5 Instruments for Protecting Owners' Right

5.1 Digital Rights Management

There are several instruments for protecting owners' interest. Digital Rights Management helps to preserve the interest of the content owners. Aside from protecting copyright holders and content creators from acts of piracy, DRM provides copyright education, securing ownership, protecting income, ensuring appropriate content access and file privacy (Digital Rights Management, n.d.). The term "digital rights management" (DRM) first appeared in the early 1990s. According to Zhang et al. (2009), the notion of DRM is used in both the business realization of contents industry sphere and research on many scientific fields, such as information technology, economics, and law. The usage of digital licensing, whereby license holders grant specific rights rather than purchasing the digital content is the fundamental idea of DRM. In essence, a digital file, the license sets forth usage guidelines for digital content, such as frequency of access, permission to copy, limitations on transferring to other devices, and more (Liu, Safavi-Naini, & Sheppard, 2003). Although copyright rules usually apply to

digital content, it can be difficult to detect illicit use of copyrighted items on the internet and in digital platforms.

5.2 DRM Technologies

5.2.1 Access control: Controlling access to resources is the primary objective of access control. It has the ability to prevent anyone from duplicating, limiting reading, altering, and sharing digital content on the internet or in digital environments. Permission management and copy protection are two crucial access control methods (Dingley & Matamoros, 2016).

5.2.2 Permission Management: The forms requesting permission to utilize copyrighted materials are granted by the content creator. Permissions that permit or unlock digital contents could include license keys, activation keys, online authentication, etc. A large number of publishers and distributors of e-books and e-journals employ internet protocol based remote authentication to control the access.

5.2.3 Copy protection: As a DRM mechanism, material creators frequently impose restrictions on the copying of their works. The technologies allow users to restrict the quantity of copies they can create or turn off the ability to copy digital content. Digital watermarking, encryption, rootkit software, and scrambling are used to limit the reproduction of digital materials.

5.2.4 Fuzzy hashing: "Fuzzy hashing" is another new technology for protecting digital document containers; it was created for audio files. The end user verifies the license information of digital contents through the use of the hash value. It's one kind of key that's utilized to query an authentication database. Users' computers may store the hash values locally or remotely (Haber et al. 2003).

5.3 Protecting by Laws

Many legal frameworks have been established to provide copyright protection for digital content within the DRM domain, such as the European Union Copyright Directive (EUCD), the US Digital Millennium Copyright Act (DMCA) of 1998, which implemented the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) Copyright Treaty and Performances and Phonograms Treaty (WIPO Treaties), the Australian Copyright Amendment (Digital Agenda) Act 2000, the Indian Copyright (Amendment) Act, 2012, which safeguards the technological measures employed by the copyright holders, and so forth (Scaria, 2012).

6 Librarians' Responsibilities

Ensuring permanent, fair access to information is a fundamental goal of libraries. It makes reasonable that libraries would support and promote open access since it aligns well with their goal (Glover, March 8, 2024). The librarians should keep the balance between two groups of users of digital contents - one is the supporter of "free access movement" and another is in favour of DRM with access control management. They should keep the notice of the followings to preserve the interest of the content owners (Khan & Porel, 2021).

- Downloading, saving, and making public any protected digital documents that are kept on the organization's server.
- Any kind of caching that keeps a copy of a resource and returns it upon request. It could take the shape of a local or shared cache.
- References or outbound links to another website with access to restricted documents without authorization;

- Scanning a copyrighted material in print copy and putting it to the website;
- Use of music, movies, software, or other pirated materials by the organization without a valid license;

Several significant factors were examined during the judgment process, including the nature of the work, the intended use, the amount of usage, the owners' loss of interest, and the possibility of financial gain for other parties.

7 Interest of Copyright Owner in OA Movements

Moral rights: The main moral rights of the authors are attribution and integrity. These moral rights are well accepted and used widely in OA movements. The authors always expect their names used by other users when they use the original works of the owners. Although, in most jurisdictions, the author must demonstrate that his reputation is at risk, the author also has the right to insist that any changes or contradictions maintain the creative integrity of his work. (Karthiayani, 2020). The rapid development of IT with AI tools has increased the possibilities of chances of violation of copyright. Therefore, today it is difficult for authors to control the use of their work in OA movements. The fundamental objective of this movement is to safeguard and advance writers' integrity, and open access does this by protecting moral rights.

The entire scholarly communications ecosystem is changing, and the shift toward open access (OA) publishing has been greatly accelerated by the open access rules of funders and other institutions (Patrick, November 14, 2023). Although open access has had a significant and long-lasting positive impact on publishing, it is also true that there are differences in open access practices and that there is no one size fits all the solutions (Alexander, 2020).

8 Conclusion

The advent of new models of publishing intellectual output is giving writers who want to publish their work a lot of options, but it's crucial to know the interest of academic writers about the benefits and drawbacks of these new models (Hoorn & Graaf, 2006). The new form of copyright enables owners to reap ever-greater rewards. Consequently, the concept of a "balance of interests" was progressively replaced with a model derived from the economic analysis of law, which describes copyright as an "incentive system" (Kretschmann, 2013).

It's unclear if funding from grants, writers, institutions, and research sponsors will convert into an open-access journal's viable business model, but money might not be their largest challenge (Denicola, & Denicola, 2011). In contrast to a copyright system with subscription costs, open access publishing that includes publication fees for writers is probably going to have various effects on economics aspects of the owners (Müller-Langer & Watt, 2010). Reverting to the balance that authorship and public interest should have, it is important to note that copyright needs to be subject to information legislation. Therefore, the right should prioritize the public interest in addition to intellectual effort when it comes to the significance of its distribution across society. The unjust competition laws may offer a viable way to resolve this dispute (Kretschmann, 2013).

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